

IMPACT OF INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY ON INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA (1986-2024)

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Abstract: *The study examined the impact of institutional quality on infrastructure development in Nigeria. The study used annual time series data covering the period of 1986 to 2024; the data for the variables were checked against the problems of unit root using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test, and all the variables were either stable or integrated at $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. Institutional quality was proxied by government effectiveness, rule of law, control of corruption, regulatory quality, and voice and accountability. At the same time, transport network, access to electricity, internet access, and mobile communication were used as proxies for the infrastructural development index. Consequently, the ADF bound test was employed, and it revealed the existence of a long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was adopted for the study, and it was discovered that the institutional quality index had a positive and significant impact on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria in the short and long periods, respectively. The result further shows that gross domestic product per capita, population growth, and inflation rate have a negative and statistically insignificant impact on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria. The overall finding revealed that institutional quality has a positive and significant effect on infrastructural development in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that policies should prioritize strengthening the effectiveness, transparency, and accountability of key institutions involved in infrastructure planning and implementation. This includes reforming regulatory bodies, improving the management capacity of public agencies, and ensuring the proper enforcement of rules and regulations.*

Keywords: *Development, Impact, Infrastructure, Institutional, Quality*

1.1. Introduction

Infrastructural development is a vital engine of economic growth and plays a pivotal role in shaping a nation's overall prosperity. It covers a wide range of physical and organizational structures, such as transportation systems, energy production, communication networks, and important public services (Muskan, 2024). These elements are essential for facilitating trade, attracting investment, and improving the quality of life for citizens. While infrastructure development is critical for all countries,

its impact can vary significantly based on the existing economic landscape, governance structures, and available resources. Infrastructure development is an important part of public investment in social and physical infrastructures (Ogunleye 2022). Infrastructure is a strategic economic growth driver. Its potentials are numerous; it serves as a catalyst for public development in the entire government agenda, such as healthcare delivery, transportation, education and food security. Infrastructure can be referred to as physical and organizational structures and facilities considered crucial in ensuring the security of any nation, its public's health, safety and its economy growth (Davies, Nwankwo, Olofinnade and Michaels, 2019). The definition of infrastructure has changed over the years; however, economic infrastructure is now commonly described as a complex array of capital goods that create services in combination with other input (World Bank, 2022).

The importance of infrastructure to the development of any nation cannot be overemphasized. Every nation that desires genuine development both economically and socially must invest in infrastructure (Kaufmann, Kraay, & Mastruzzi, 2011). Investment especially in infrastructure is capital-intensive, and it requires enormous investment because of its importance in pivoting economic growth and development. Lack of investment in infrastructure will resultantly lead to an infrastructural deficit with great consequences for human welfare and national development. The infrastructure role can be important for development in the sense that it provides both final consumption services to households and key intermediate consumption items for production (Sabir, Rafique, & Abbas, 2019). Infrastructure is argued to be one of the critical factors for economic growth in the low-income countries like Nigeria. Efficient infrastructure can promote sustainable economic and social development (Abubakar, 2020). Infrastructural development of any nation is the creation of basic foundational services to enhance economic growth and quality of life. Infrastructure level affects the developmental ratings of a nation. According to Adegboye, et al, (2023), infrastructure can also improve the quality of life for many people through increasing the value of consumption, enhancing labor productivity and creation of job opportunities. The realization of the importance of infrastructure was acknowledged in the global circle as it constitutes one of the cardinal agenda of the sustainable development goals (SDGs). The United Nations (UN) has stipulated 17 cardinal goals to be achieved within a specific time frame by developing nations. They include: poverty eradication, good health care and wellbeing, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry, innovation and infrastructure, and reduction of inequality. The SDGs have revolved around the achievement of human wellbeing and accelerated development in all nations. It might be difficult and unsustainable to achieve all these goals without vigorous and sustained infrastructural development in all the countries in the world, especially in developing countries, where the attempt to achieve national development has been a mirage.

1.2. Statement of the problem

The development of infrastructure in Nigeria has been significantly influenced by various factors, among which institutional quality stands out as a critical determinant. Despite the country's rich

resources and potential for economic growth, infrastructural deficits persist, inhibiting sustainable development and exacerbating socio-economic inequalities. Institutional quality, encompassing aspects such as governance, regulatory frameworks, accountability, and transparency, directly impacts the planning, financing, and execution of infrastructure projects. In Nigeria, weak institutions often lead to inefficiencies, corruption, and poor project management, resulting in suboptimal infrastructure development. Consequently, there exists a pressing need to examine how variations in institutional quality affect infrastructure initiatives, particularly in sectors such as transportation, energy, and water supply.

This study aims to identify and analyze the relationship between institutional quality and infrastructure development in Nigeria. It seeks to understand the mechanisms through which institutional factors influence project outcomes and to provide insights into how enhancing institutional frameworks can lead to more effective and sustainable infrastructure development. Ultimately, the findings will inform policymakers and stakeholders about strategies to strengthen institutional capacities, thereby promoting overall national growth and development.

1.3. Objective of the study

The broad objective of this research is to examine the impact of institutional quality on infrastructure development in Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

- i. To examine the impact of institutional quality on infrastructure development in Nigeria.
- ii. To evaluate the moderating effect of institutional and government capital expenditure on infrastructure development in Nigeria.

1.4. Hypothesis of the study

The following null hypotheses will be tested:

- i. Ho1: Institutional quality has no significant impact on infrastructure development in Nigeria.
- ii. Ho2: The Moderating effect of institutional quality and government capital expenditure have no significant impact on infrastructure development in Nigeria.
- iii. To determine the direction of causality between institutional quality and infrastructure development in Nigeria.

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Institutional Quality

Institutional quality is a concept that relates to law, the rights of individual and the sophistication of government regulation and services. Institutional quality and economic performance are closely related. It is argued that institutional quality plays a crucial role in this relationship. Institutional development brings to the fore growth potentials, and it is often not affected by diminishing returns. Data has shown that regions or countries with excellent institutional quality display much success in adopting frontier technology and higher productivity levels since the beginning of this millennium. (Boujelbene, 2021). Institutional quality refers to the effectiveness, efficiency, and integrity of the

institutions that govern a society. These institutions include formal rules (such as laws and constitutions), informal norms (like cultural practices), and enforcement mechanisms that guide economic, political, and social interactions. High institutional quality is often associated with transparency, accountability, the rule of law, and low levels of corruption.

According to North (1990), institutions are "the rules of the game" in a society, shaping the incentives of political and economic actors. Institutional quality thus determines how well these rules are designed and implemented. In recent years, empirical research has emphasized the centrality of institutional quality in achieving sustainable development, reducing poverty, and enhancing economic performance (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; World Bank, 2023). Modern assessments of institutional quality typically involve indices such as the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), which include dimensions like government effectiveness, regulatory quality, control of corruption, and rule of law (Kaufmann, Kraay, & Mastruzzi, 2011). Countries with higher institutional quality tend to attract more investment, maintain better public services, and exhibit higher levels of trust in government (OECD, 2022). Recent studies also underscore the role of institutional resilience, especially in the wake of global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, institutions that are adaptable and inclusive have been more successful in managing health and economic shocks (IMF, 2024).

2.1.2. Infrastructure Development

Infrastructure development is a broad concept that embraces public investment in physical assets and social services. Infrastructure development refers to the process of building, improving, and maintaining the foundational physical and organizational structures necessary for the functioning of a society. This includes facilities such as transportation networks, energy supply systems, communication infrastructure, water resources, and public institutions (Adeniran, & Alimi, 2020). It plays a critical role in fostering economic growth, enhancing connectivity, and improving the quality of life for individuals. Recent developments have heightened interest in infrastructure development in both developed and developing countries. Much emphasis has actually been placed on the role of infrastructure in mitigating the recent global financial crisis through stimulus packages in developed countries and the recurring attention on its impact on growth and poverty reduction in developing countries.

According to Oladipo, & Akinwale,(2020), infrastructure development can be viewed from a broad perspective as it embraces public investments not just in physical assets, alone, but also in social services. The definition of the concept of infrastructure has been a subject of debate among scholars and practitioners. Despite the controversies that trail the meaning of infrastructure, there is an agreement that infrastructure constitutes amenities such as good roads and rail networks, health care facilities, and rural or urban electrification, among others, which enhance the well-being of the people and also lead to national development. The term 'infrastructure', according to Oladipo, & Akinwale,(2022), was first used in the late 1880s. The term is a combination of the Latin prefix 'infra' – meaning below, and the French word 'structure' – meaning building. This connotes the foundation upon which a building is laid. This implies that infrastructure is the foundation upon which the structure of

every economy is laid. Thus, the survival and development of the economy of any nation are predicated on the availability of infrastructure.

2.1.3. Government Capital Expenditure

Government capital expenditure refers to public spending on long-term assets that create productive capacity, including physical infrastructure, institutional facilities, and technology systems. In the context of Nigeria, capital expenditure is critical for building and sustaining institutional infrastructure that supports governance, economic activity, education, health, and trade (Adeniran & Olayemi, 2019). Unlike recurrent expenditure, which covers salaries, administrative costs, and routine operations, capital expenditure focuses on investments that yield future benefits by enhancing the efficiency, capacity, and effectiveness of public institutions.

Institutional infrastructure encompasses the legal, regulatory, and organizational frameworks within which economic and social activities occur. Effective institutional infrastructure requires investments in government buildings, courts, universities, research laboratories, ICT networks, transportation systems, and public utilities (Ogunleye, 2018). Government capital expenditure in these areas strengthens institutional capacity, facilitates service delivery, reduces operational bottlenecks, and improves the overall business and governance environment. For example, investment in modern courts, e-governance systems, and regulatory agencies ensures faster contract enforcement, better policy implementation, and more transparent public administration, which are critical for economic growth and development.

Empirical studies indicate that in Nigeria, the level and efficiency of capital expenditure on institutional infrastructure significantly affect national development outcomes. According to Adegboye, et al (2020), inadequate capital expenditure on institutional infrastructure leads to weak governance systems, poor public service delivery, and low investor confidence. Conversely, targeted investment in institutional capacity enhances accountability, reduces bureaucratic inefficiencies, and fosters socio-economic development. In the context of education and research, capital expenditure on universities, research centers, and libraries improves the quality of human capital and knowledge generation, which in turn strengthens national competitiveness.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

One major theory that forms a basis for this topic is the Endogenous Growth Theory, as presented by Romer (1986) and Robert Lucas Jr. (1988). This theory posits that economic growth in the long term can be sustained by internal factors such as the development of human capital, innovation, and government investments in infrastructure, as opposed to external factors. Institutional infrastructure, including education systems, laws, regulatory agencies, and ICT infrastructure, boosts economic efficiency as well as innovation through the creation of an enabling environment for economic activities. Government capital expenditure in institutional infrastructure boosts economic growth through efficiency, knowledge creation, and investments (Romer, 1986; Lucas, 1988).

Another relevant framework is the New Institutional Economics (NIE) theory, which was proposed by Douglass North (1990). North contends that institutions, which include laws, regulations, and modes of governance, play a crucial role in the performance of the economy by reducing uncertainty and transaction costs. In the Nigerian context, the level of institutional infrastructure, such as the development of judicial institutions, anti-corruption agencies, public financial management institutions, and regulatory institutions, influences the effectiveness of economic policy implementation. Inefficient institutional infrastructure contributes to increased levels of corruption and policy inconsistency, leading to developmental challenges.

The study can equally be grounded in the theory of public expenditure, which was expounded by Wagner's Law, as presented by Adolph Wagner (1893). Wagner's Law simply posits that as economic development increases in a particular country, so does government expenditure, especially in areas such as infrastructure development, education, and institutional development. In developing economies such as Nigeria, for instance, there is a need for the government to increase its capital expenditure in developing institutional infrastructure.

Moreover, the Institutional Development Theory developed by Daron Acemoglu and James A. Robinson (2012) stresses that effective and inclusive institutions are a major factor to consider for economic growth within a particular nation. For instance, countries with well-established institutional systems to safeguard property rights, uphold contracts, and maintain political stability have shown higher economic development outcomes. Consequently, investing in institutional infrastructure within Nigeria, including governance systems, digital administration systems, and modernizing institutional regulations, can greatly impact economic growth within the nation.

3 Methodology

This study adopts an ex-post facto research design, using secondary data to examine the relationship between institutional quality and infrastructural development in Nigeria. The choice of this type of design also allowed the researcher the privilege of observing variables over a long period of time (1986-2024). Data for the study were sourced from World Development Indicators, 2024 (WDI, 2024). The dependent variable for the study is the infrastructural development index (IDI) as a proxy for infrastructural development. The independent variables are institutional quality, gross domestic product per capita, government capital expenditure, population growth, and inflation rate. Data on infrastructure development, institutional quality, gross domestic product per capita, government capital expenditure, population growth, and inflation rate were sourced from World Development Indicators, 2024. Data for the study were subjected to preliminary tests to ascertain the behavior of the data set. The data was analyzed with econometric techniques involving Descriptive Statistics, Augmented Dickey Fuller Tests for Unit Root

Roots, cointegration test, and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Approach.

The most famous test to do so is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller

(ADF) and the Phillips-Petron (PP) unit-root tests. The ADF test is the test of a particular series, say, Y_t , such that;

$$\Delta y_t = \delta y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad \mathbf{3.1}$$

The method to be applied in this study is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test.

The ADF equation is stated below:

$$\Delta y_t = \delta y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \mu_t \quad \mathbf{3.2}$$

The testing procedure follows an examination of the student-t ratio for δ . The critical values of the test are all negative and larger in absolute terms than standard critical t-values, so they are called DF and ADF statistics. If the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, then the series Y_t cannot be stationary.

Decision Rule:

Reject H_0 if the absolute DF or ADF t-statistic > 5% critical values. If otherwise, accept H_0 .

Model Specification

To investigate the empirical relationship between institutional quality and infrastructural development, this study followed the works of Badiru (2023) as the foundation for the model. However, this study introduced population growth and inflation rate as control variables in the model.

$$IDI = f(IQI, GDP_{pc}, GOVE, POPG, INF) \quad \mathbf{3.4}$$

Where;

IDI = Infrastructural Development Index used as a proxy for infrastructural development;

IQI= Institutional Quality Index;

GDP pc = Gross Domestic Product per capita;

GOVE = Government capital expenditure;

POPG = Population growth;

INF= Inflation rate;

Econometrically, equations (3.3&3.4) can be represented in a linear form as:

$$IDI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IQI_t + \beta_2 GDP_{pc,t} + \beta_3 \ln GOVE_t + \beta_4 \ln POPG_t + \beta_5 \ln INF_t + \mu_t \quad \mathbf{3.5}$$

To address the two questions on whether government capital expenditure moderates the impact of institutional quality on infrastructural development, Eq (3.5) is augmented to include the interaction term, and the moderation model is expressed as

$$IDI_t = \alpha_t + \beta_1 IQI_t + \beta_2 GDP_{pc,t} + \beta_3 GOVE_t + \beta_4 IQI * \ln GOVE_t + \beta_5 \ln POPG_t + \beta_6 SCR_t + \beta_7 \ln INF_t + \mu_t \quad \mathbf{3.6}$$

$IQI \times \ln GOVE$ denotes the interaction term between institutional quality index and government capital expenditure, which is used to investigate how government capital expenditure moderates the effect of institutional quality on infrastructural development. Also, this study is particularly interested in the marginal effect of a change in institutional quality index on infrastructural development, and how this change is influenced by the level of government capital expenditure. Hence, the marginal effect is computed via the partial derivative of Equation (3.6) with respect to government capital expenditure.

This partial derivative of the institutional quality variable with respect to government capital expenditure is given by:

$$\frac{\partial IDI_t}{\partial \ln GOVE} = [1/(1 - \phi t)](\beta_1 + \beta_3 IQI) \quad \mathbf{3.7}$$

Thus, the focal point of this study is on the coefficients in the partial derivative equation. If $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_3 < 0$, it implies that the institutional quality index is a blessing while the government capital expenditure is adversely influencing that blessing. The adverse influence of public expenditure diminishes as government capital expenditure improves, indicating that whether the institutional quality index is a blessing or curse depends on the level of government capital expenditure in an economy, which suggests the presence of a threshold effect. If $\beta_1 < 0$ and $\beta_3 > 0$, it signals that institutional quality is a curse while government capital expenditure moderates that curse in Nigeria. However, if the two parameters are positive, it signals that an increase in institutional quality would be a blessing to Nigeria's economy, and improved government capital expenditure would intensify that blessing. However, if the two parameters carry negative signs, it signals that an increase in the institutional quality index would lead to a decrease in infrastructural development, while ineffective government capital expenditure would heighten the decrease.

The ARDL approach to long co-integration relationship involves estimating the unrestricted Error correction model (ECM) model and has been identified following Pesaran et al (2001) below as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta IDI_t = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 \Delta IDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_2 \Delta IQI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=3}^p \beta_3 \Delta GDPpc_{t-i} + \sum_{i=4}^p \beta_4 GOVE + \sum_{i=5}^p \beta_5 \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=6}^p \beta_6 \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=7}^p \beta_7 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \alpha_1 IDI_{t-1} + \alpha_2 IQI_{t-1} + \alpha_3 GDPpct_{-i} + \alpha_4 GOVE_{t-i} + \alpha_5 POPG_{t-i} + \\ & \alpha_6 INF_{t-i} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \quad \mathbf{3.8}$$

The optimal Lag length test has been conducted by means of the lag length criteria (which is the AIC) to obtain the optimal number of lags for each variable. This was followed by the estimation of a single equation unrestricted error correction model with the number of selected lags as shown in Equation (3.4).

To obtain the short-run coefficients, the short-run model is specified as follows: -

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta IDI_t = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 \Delta IDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_2 \Delta IQI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=3}^p \beta_3 \Delta GDPpc_{t-i} + \sum_{i=4}^p \beta_4 GOVE + \sum_{i=5}^p \beta_5 \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=6}^p \beta_6 \Delta POPG_{t-i} + \sum_{i=7}^p \beta_7 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \alpha_1 IDI_{t-1} + \alpha_2 IQI_{t-1} + \alpha_3 GDPpct_{-i} + \alpha_4 GOVE_{t-i} + \alpha_5 POPG_{t-i} + \alpha_6 INF_{t-i} \\ & ++ \lambda ECT_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned} \quad \mathbf{3.9}$$

Where;

ECT_{t-1} is the error correction term lagged by one period,

Δ is the first difference operator; p is the optimal lag length and all other variables remain the same in the model; ECT is the error correction term; λ in equation (3.9) represents the speed of adjustment while the other coefficients ($\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \dots \alpha_8$) of the short-run equation are coefficients relating to the short-run dynamics of the model's convergence to equilibrium; $\beta_1 - \beta_8$ are long-run coefficients; and μ_t is the white noise error term.

The *a priori* expectations are:

$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 > 0, \delta > 0, \epsilon < 0.$

4. Presentation and Analysis of Data

This section of the study presents the empirical analysis, results, and discussion of findings. The section also includes descriptive analysis, unit root test analysis, cointegration test using the bounds cointegration test, estimation using ARDL, and post-estimation tests

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1.1: Result of Descriptive Statistics

	IDI	IQI	GDPPC	GOVE	POPG	INF
Mean	0.232653	-0.061088	1.454217	795.1384	2.598373	19.56418
Median	-0.668566	-1.114388	1.437691	508.7488	2.657389	12.94178
Maximum	5.048558	3.275151	12.21039	4486.206	2.802785	72.83550
Minimum	-2.125872	-3.537405	-4.597233	6.372500	2.092817	5.388008
Std. Dev.	2.220349	2.079278	3.618476	962.2542	0.214460	17.11452
Skewness	0.692455	0.433600	0.544054	2.075462	-1.415788	1.757983
Kurtosis	2.249471	1.690761	3.676241	7.590096	3.749435	4.885890
Jarque-Bera	3.928678	3.904727	2.598692	60.64032	13.58417	25.20445
Probability	0.140249	0.141938	0.272710	0.000000	0.001123	0.000003
Sum	8.840804	-2.321339	55.26026	30215.26	98.73819	743.4389
Sum Sq. Dev.	182.4082	159.9657	484.4547	34259524	1.701740	10837.55
Observations	38	38	38	38	38	38

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive analysis of the time series properties of the variables included in the model. The average value of infrastructural development index, institutional quality index, gross domestic product per capita, government capital expenditure, population growth and inflation rate are 0.232653, -0.061088, 1.454217, 795.1384, 2.598373 and 19.56418 respectively. The standard deviation which shows the nature of dispersal in the worth of the variables is small, which reveals that there has not been much increase in the value of the variables over the years considered for this study except for government expenditures. The mean of the variables falls within the range defined by the minimum and maximum values of the variables. Infrastructural development index, institutional quality index, and gross domestic product per capita, government capital expenditure and inflation rate have positive skewness indicating they have a long right tale, while population growth has negative skewness implying, it has a long-left tale. The kurtosis of the variables is above 3, except for infrastructural development index and institutional quality index which are below 3 implying that most of the variable's distribution is thin and would turn leptokurtic. While gross domestic product per capita and population growth are exactly 3 platykurtic. The Jarque-Bera statistics mean the series is not normally

distributed, with probability values greater than 0.05, but the normality assumption is not usually required for multivariate functions

4.1.2 Unit Root Test

The unit root test carried out is based on the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test at a 5 per cent level of significance.

Table 4.2: Result of Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test

Variables	Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)		Dickey-Fuller		Order of Integration
	At Level	5% Critical Value	At First Difference	5% Critical Value	
IDI	0.169352	-2.941145	-6.326514	-2.943427	I(1)
IQI	-2.059807	-2.943427	-18.80498	-2.943427	I(1)
GDPpc	-4.276790	-2.941145	---	---	I(0)
lnGOVE	-1.474704	-2.943427	-6.891725	-2.945842	I(1)
POPg	-3.113283	-2.954021	---	---	I(0)
INF	-3.584477	-2.943427	---	---	I(0)

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

Based on the above result of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, the variables are mixture I(1) and I(0) and are significant at a 5 per cent level. Under the ADF approach, infrastructural development index (IDI), institutional quality index (IQI), and government capital expenditure (lnGOVE) were all integrated at first difference, I(1), while gross domestic product per capita (GDPpc), population growth (POPg), and inflation rate (INF) are stationary at levels form, I(0). Therefore, since our variables are in mixed order of integration, the analysis considers this by employing the ARDL approach to the error correction mechanism.

4.1.3 ARDL (Bounds) Test for Cointegration for Model 1

Table 4.3 Result of the ARDL (Bounds) Test for Cointegration for the infrastructure development and economic growth Model.

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistics (IDI, IQI, GOVE, POPG, INF)	5.919051	6
Critical Value Bounds,		
Significance	Io Bound	I1 Bound
10%	1.99	2.94
5%	2.27	3.28
2.5%	2.55	3.61
1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

Table 4.3 is the ARDL bound test result, which reveals that there is a long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the model. The test result showed that the F-statistic, which is 5.919051, is above the upper bound critical values I (1) at all the levels of significance, indicating the existence of a long-run relationship in the model. Based on this result, the study conducted the short-run and long-run forms of the ARDL model.

4.2 Estimates of institutional quality and infrastructure development Using the ARDL Approach

The short-run dynamic relationship between infrastructure development and economic growth in Nigeria, as estimated by the ARDL model, is reported below in Table 4.5.

Table 4.4 Result of Short Run ARDL Vector Error Correction

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IDI(-1))	-0.015172	0.086020	-0.176382	0.8625
D(IDI(-2))	-0.345227	0.083505	-4.134178	0.0010
D(IQI)	4.516872	0.418548	10.79177	0.0000
D(IQI(-1))	-0.355998	0.289447	-1.229925	0.2390
D(IQI(-2))	1.234255	0.288347	4.280446	0.0008
D(IQI_LNGOVE)	-0.832736	0.077879	-10.69274	0.0000
D(IQI_LNGOVE(-1))	-0.016339	0.052812	-0.309382	0.7616
D(IQI_LNGOVE(-2))	-0.217958	0.048648	-4.480305	0.0005
D(GDPPC)	-0.050989	0.011865	-4.297340	0.0007
D(LNGOVE)	0.601048	0.143325	4.193592	0.0009
D(LNGOVE(-1))	-1.463536	0.265831	-5.505503	0.0001
D(LNGOVE(-2))	-0.640947	0.197326	-3.248172	0.0058
D(POPG)	-3.585717	0.970815	-3.693513	0.0024
CointEq(-1)*	-1.209023	0.143456	-8.427847	0.0000
R-squared	0.881784	Mean dependent var		0.190217
Adjusted R-squared	0.808603	S.D. dependent var		0.502675
S.E. of regression	0.219915	Akaike info criterion		0.098021
Sum squared resid	1.015613	Schwarz criterion		0.720161
Log likelihood	12.28463	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.312784
Durbin-Watson stat	2.409535			

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

Table 4.4 above presents the result of the short-run estimates of the ARDL model.

The lagged one-period value of the coefficient of the infrastructural development index rate had a negative and statistically insignificant impact on itself. But the lag of two periods had a negative but significant impact on the current infrastructural development

The institutional quality index had a positive and statistically significant impact on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria. The sign of the coefficient of the institutional quality index (IQI) is in line with the a priori expectation. However, the lagged one period showed that the institutional quality index had a negative and statistically insignificant impact on the infrastructural development index, while the lagged two periods had a positive and significant impact on the infrastructure development index. This implies that a one percent increase in the institutional quality index would lead to a 4.51 percent increase in the infrastructural development index. This finding, which is consistent with the findings of Flachaire et al. (2014) and Kodongo and Ojah (2016), suggests that Africa's level of institutional quality and the channels through which the institutional quality transmits to economic growth require greater attention to enhance economic growth on the continent.

Furthermore, the interactive effect of the institutional quality index and government capital expenditure was revealed to have a negative and significant effect on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria. However, one lagged period showed a negative and insignificant effect on the infrastructural development index, whereas in the lagged two periods, it had a negative and statistically significant effect on the infrastructural development index. The coefficient of the interactive term is negative in all the cases. This finding indicates that the interaction term has a negative relationship with infrastructural development. Since the coefficients of the institutional quality index and the interaction term have different signs, it shows that the institutional quality index is weak, while government capital expenditure is positively moderating that weakness towards becoming better or improved. This implies that as government capital expenditure is spent judiciously or improves in Nigeria, it goes a long way to strengthen our institutions, thereby making institutional quality be carried out and implemented gainfully, so they would then be capable of stimulating more infrastructural development in the country. This implies that a one percent increase in the interaction term would inversely lead to a 0.83 percent increase in the infrastructural development index.

The coefficient of gross domestic product per capita has a negative but statistically significant impact on the infrastructural development index. This result does not agree with the a priori expectation. This indicates that a one percent increase in gross domestic product per capita would lead to a -0.051 percent decrease in the infrastructural development index.

Also, the coefficient of government capital expenditure has a positive and statistically significant impact on the infrastructural development index. However, in lagged 1 and 2 periods, it has a negative but significant impact on the infrastructural development index. The result reveals that population growth has a negative but significant relationship with the infrastructural development index (IDI). This conforms with the a priori expectation, and this denotes that one percent in population growth would lead to -3.585% decrease in infrastructural development in the country.

The error correction model (ECM) is expected to meet three conditions: it must be negative, less than one, and significant. Therefore, based on the result in the table above, the ECM has a negative value of (-1.209023), and it has a probability value (P-value) of 0.0000, which is significant; this denotes that the speed of adjustment from disequilibrium in the preceding period to the recent period is correctly signed and statistically significant (Narayan & Smyth 2005). Hence, as a result of differencing the variable, the unit root is corrected at a speed of 21% as shown by the coefficient of ECM (-1) from the result. It can be deduced that the ECM (-1) coefficient is negative and significant at 5% level of significance. The R-squared with a value of 0.881784 indicates that the regressors employed in this model are responsible for approximately 88 percent of the variation in infrastructural development, while the remaining 12 percent of the variation in infrastructural development is influenced by other variables not included in this model.

4.2.1 Long Run Estimates for Model 1

Table 4.6 Result of Long-run Coefficient estimates

Selected model: (3,3,3,1,3,1,0)	ARDL			
Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IQI	3.823811	0.465710	8.210715	0.0000
IQI_LNGOVE	-0.613317	0.052513	-11.67926	0.0000
GDPPC	-0.078172	0.043663	-1.790325	0.0950
LNGOVE	1.779448	0.208130	8.549684	0.0000
POPG	-0.373498	0.720687	-0.518253	0.6124
INF	-0.009706	0.008235	-1.178649	0.2582
C	-9.646433	2.806641	-3.437003	0.0040

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

Table 4.6 above shows the long-run result of ARDL estimation. The institutional quality index had a positive and significant impact on infrastructural development in Nigeria. The sign of the coefficient of the institutional quality index (IQI) agrees with the a priori expectation. This implies that a one percent increase in the institutional quality index would lead to a 3.82 percent increase in the infrastructural development index in Nigeria.

However, the result reveals that the interactive term has a significant negative relationship with the infrastructural development index in the long run; it further reveals that the interaction between the institutional quality index and government capital expenditure has a negative but significant effect on the infrastructural development index. These findings align with the works of Nair, Arvin, Pradhan, & Bahmani (2021). Also, gross domestic product per capita, population growth, and inflation rate have a negative and statistically insignificant impact on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria. The

result further revealed that government capital expenditure has a positive and significant impact on the infrastructural development index in Nigeria.

4.3 Granger Causality Test

In examining the nature of the relationship between infrastructure development, economic growth, and poverty, the result of the Pairwise Granger causality test is presented in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7 Pairwise Granger causality test result

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
IQI does not Granger Cause IDI	38	1.20105	0.2806
IDI does not Granger Cause IQI		3.03501	0.0903
IQI_LNGOVE does not Granger Cause IDI	37	0.61924	0.4368
IDI does not Granger Cause IQI_LNGOVE		15.4320	0.0004
GDPPC does not Granger Cause IDI	38	0.01145	0.9154
IDI does not Granger Cause GDPPC		0.27716	0.6019
LNGOVE does not Granger Cause IDI	37	2.13935	0.1527
IDI does not Granger Cause LNGOVE		0.43978	0.5117
POPG does not Granger Cause IDI	38	0.12157	0.7294
IDI does not Granger Cause POPG		3.96286	0.0544
INF does not Granger Cause IDI	38	2.45578	0.1261
IDI does not Granger Cause INF		0.71645	0.4031

Source: Author's Computation, E-views version 12

4.4 Diagnostic Tests for the model

The estimated ARDL model is tested for heteroscedasticity, serial correlation, functional form misspecification, parameter stability, and normality. The results from these tests are shown below:

4.4.1 Normality Test

Figure 2: Test for Normality of the Residuals 9

Series: Residuals	
Sample 1989 2023	
Observations 35	
Mean	-6.54e-15
Median	-0.035534
Maximum	0.481916
Minimum	-0.368563
Std. Dev.	0.172832
Skewness	0.325941
Kurtosis	3.400232
Jarque-Bera	0.853322
Probability	0.652685

H_0 : Null hypothesis: Residual is multivariate normal, H_1 : Alternative hypothesis: Residual is not multivariate normal. Consideration of the Jacque-Bera statistic with value 2.460021 and Prob. value of 0.652685, which is greater than the 0.05 level. Hence, we accept the H_0 that the residual is normally distributed. Therefore, the study concluded that the residual of the model is normally distributed.

Table 4.8. Other Diagnostic Tests of the Selected ARDL Model

Test Statistics	P-value
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.2725
Heteroskedasticity Test	0.7791
Ramsey RESET Test	0.6982

Source: Authors' computation, E-views version 12

The estimated ARDL model revealed that the model passed the serial correlation, normal test, heteroscedasticity, and Ramsey RESET tests. The error terms were uncorrelated, normally distributed, had the same variance, and the model was not misspecified. Thus, they were satisfactory for the ARDL model.

4.4.2 Stability Tests

The graphs in Figures 3 and 4 show that our model is stable. Its stability is explained with the blue line within the upper and lower bound red lines. The above plot, remaining within the critical bounds of the 5% significance level, also reveals that our model is correctly specified.

Figure 3: Plot of CUSUM- Result of Stability Test

Figure 4: Plot of CUSUMSQ- Result of Stability Test

Both plots lie between the critical bounds at the 5% significance level. This indicates that the model is stable and can therefore be reliably deployed for policy purposes.

4.5 Evaluation of Research Hypotheses

From the estimated results, the following hypothesis testing was found;

4.5.1 Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Institutional quality has no significant impact on infrastructure development in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the probability value of the institutional quality index is less than 0.05. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is not to be rejected at a 5 percent level of significance.

Conclusion: The result presented in tables 4.5 & 4.6 shows the probability values of the infrastructure development index to be less than 0.05 ($P(t) = 0.0000, 0.0000 < 0.05$) both in the short and long run

ARDL estimates. Therefore, the null hypothesis is to be rejected in the short and long run, respectively. This implies that the institutional quality index has a significant impact on infrastructural development in Nigeria.

4.5.2 Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: The Moderating effect of institutional quality and government capital expenditure has no significant impact on infrastructure development in Nigeria. **Decision Rule:** Reject the null hypothesis if the probability value of the multiplicative interactive term is less than 0.05. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is not to be rejected at a 5 percent level of significance.

Conclusion: The result presented in tables 4.4 & 4.5 shows the probability values of the interactive term to be less than 0.05 ($P(t) = 0.0000, 0.0000 < 0.05$) in the short and long run ARDL estimates, respectively. Therefore, the null hypothesis is to be rejected in the model. This indicates that the interaction of the institutional quality index and government capital expenditure has a significant effect on infrastructural development in Nigeria.

4.5.3 Hypothesis Three

Ho₄: There is no causal relationship between institutional quality and infrastructure development in Nigeria

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the probability value of the F-statistic of pairs is less than 0.05. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is not to be rejected at a 5 percent level of significance.

Conclusion: The result presented in Table 4.7 shows the probability value of the F-statistic of pairs to be greater than 0.05 per cent, $IQI \leftrightarrow IDI (0.2806, 0.0903)$. This simply means that there is no causal relationship between the institutional quality index and the infrastructure development index in Nigeria, within the period under study.

4.6 Discussion of results

This study examined the nexus between institutional quality and infrastructural development in Nigeria. Annual Secondary Time series data of 39 years were obtained from World Bank Development indicator, 2024. Descriptive statistic and unit root test was conducted and the unit root test results showed that infrastructural development index, institutional quality index and government capital expenditure were all integrated at first difference, $I(1)$ while gross domestic product per capita, population growth and inflation rate are stationary at levels form, $I(0)$. Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound test established that there exists a long run relationship between institutional quality and infrastructural development in Nigeria. The empirical result showed that institutional quality index has a positive and statistically significant impact on infrastructural development index in Nigeria, both in the short and long run.

5. Conclusion

The study examined the role of institutional quality on infrastructural development in Nigeria. The study also examined the causal relationship between the quality of institutions and infrastructural development based on time series data over the period of 1986–2024. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller

unit root test was applied to all selected variables. The study employed the ARDL cointegration approach; based on the findings, it was discovered that the institutional quality index has a long-run effect on infrastructural development in Nigeria. The study further revealed that the interaction of the institutional quality index and government capital expenditure is negatively related to infrastructural development in Nigeria in the short and long periods, respectively, but statistically significant. Also, gross domestic product per capita has a negative but statistically significant impact on the infrastructural development index in the short run, while it has a negative but insignificant impact on the infrastructural development index.

However, government capital expenditure has a positive and statistically significant impact on the infrastructural development index in the short run, whereas it has a positive but insignificant impact on the infrastructural development index. The study further shows that population growth has a negative but significant relationship with the infrastructural development index in the short run. However, it has a negative and insignificant effect on the infrastructural development index. Lastly, the study reveals that there was no causal relationship between institutional quality and the infrastructure development index. The diagnostic tests show that the model is free from autocorrelation residuals, correctly specified, has a normal distribution, and constant finite variance. Also, the CUSUM and the CUMSUMSQ show that the short-run and the long-run estimates are stable.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proffered:

- i. Given that institutional quality has a positive and significant impact on infrastructure development, policies should prioritize strengthening the effectiveness, transparency, and accountability of key institutions involved in infrastructure planning and implementation.
- ii. The study revealed a negative relationship between government capital expenditure and infrastructure development when combined with institutional quality, suggesting that increased capital spending without adequate institutional oversight can be counterproductive. Therefore, the government should ensure that capital expenditures are directed towards projects with strong institutional backing and clear oversight mechanisms.
- iii. Given the lack of a causal relationship between institutional quality and infrastructure development, further research should be conducted to understand the underlying factors and mechanisms affecting infrastructure outcomes. This research should focus on identifying the critical institutional factors that hinder or promote infrastructure development in different regions of Nigeria.

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